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BREAKING THE TYRANNY OF CONTENT IN CURRICULUM DESIGN: A WORKSHOP SYNTHESISING AFFECTIVE, COGNITIVE AND FUNCTIONALIST CONSTRUCTS

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INTRODUCTION

Participation in this workshop will introduce colleagues to a new way of looking at curriculum design based upon a distinctive approach that has been developed by colleagues at WMG, University of Warwick. Initially created for use in the design of the new Advanced Professional Engineering Programme (APEP), the approach, which is grounded in the three concepts associated with the Engineering Habits of Mind Study ('Heart', 'Hand' and 'Head'), introduces the Three Pillars of Curriculum Design (Affective, Cognitive, Functional).

The workshop will provide colleagues with an opportunity to actively participate in the new design process; working in small groups we will explore the need to align programme specific learning outcomes with professional body standards and employer expectations to develop a curriculum design which is authentic across the three pillars.

THE LITERATURE

Comprising an essential part of Engineering Education, Curriculum Design is usually underpinned by a complex mixture of wider educational theory including Constructive Alignment [1] and Concept Mapping [2], and discipline-specific theoretical approaches which have emerged out of Engineering Education Research (See for example [3], [4]).

In Engineering Education the approach to curriculum design is further complicated by the requirements of accrediting bodies and, in the case of Degree Apprenticeships in

the UK, by the requirements of apprenticeship standards – developed by ‘Trailblazer’ groups of employers. A frequent criticism of the design of engineering courses is that they are too content focused. As Rompelman and De Graaf [4] note, often ‘a curriculum is described on the basis of the contents by summing up the modules’. This approach creates an input rather than output-focused approach, causing issues including cohesiveness of the curriculum and authenticity of the learning experience. In looking at the relevant literature, the concept of Signature Pedagogies [5] represents an important epistemological standpoint as it encapsulates an applied pedagogy in which the *habits of head, hand and heart* are central drivers in how the curriculum is designed and delivered [6]. Taking this notion one step further and grounded in the Engineering Habits of Mind concept proposed by Lucas and Hanson [7], the tripartite approach developed in WMG represents a holistic model of student development in which three distinctive yet interlinked pillars of curriculum design, representing the affective, cognitive and functional aspects of education are given equal consideration in developing a more connected and ‘holistic’ design approach [8].

Figure 1: The Three Pillars of Curriculum Design: The EIG Approach

WORKSHOP AIM

Grounded in the emergent findings of our study, the workshop activity is designed to help colleagues get to grips with the practical design of Engineering Education programmes using signature pedagogies. Using the case of a new open Degree Apprenticeship programme in engineering, the workshop will illustrate how approaches such as Signature Pedagogies and Threshold Concepts can be combined to energise staff around developing a programme which is driven by the vision of the Engineer developed through the programme, and not by the technical content of the programme.

WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS

The workshop has been purposefully developed so as to whet the appetite of those colleagues who are interested in evolutionally and revolutionary curriculum design. It is equally suitable for colleagues who have previously participated in design activities and those with little or no experience. Useful preparation for the session would be to look at the Miro platform ([An Online Whiteboard & Visual Collaboration Platform for Teamwork | Miro](#)) which is free for educational applications at time of writing, but this is not a requirement.

WORKSHOP FORMAT

a. Introduction to Design Principles: 5 Minutes

A quick summary of the principles to be applied over the workshop

b. Group Activity (1): Fast-Forward to Basics: A course in a tweet: 10 minutes

Start from the 'Why'; focusing on the central purpose of the programme you have 140 characters to create a compelling vision for potential students and industrial partners.

c. Group Discussion: Feedback to identify themes and issues: 5 minutes

What can we learn from the exercise? Focused reflection in action.

d. Group Activity (2): Using Miro to collaboratively design a curriculum guided by the 3 pillars: 25 minutes

Two-for-one: a quick engagement with the collaborative design software Miro, which has been transformational in our ability to work together online in WMG and to build a curriculum from a principle-led, outcome-focused perspective.

e. Facilitated Discussion: Applying the Three Pillars Approach to bespoke institutional settings: 15 minutes

Reflection on action to consider how the lessons from this session might be applied in your context.

WORKSHOP OUTPUTS AND OUTCOMES

1. A better understanding of the complex link between pedagogy and design
2. The opportunity to engage with colleagues in an active, focused discussion around the challenges of curriculum design in engineering
3. Application of Miro boards in course and module design.
4. Knowledge of a distinctive and innovative approach to curriculum design which may be adopted and adapted to a range of engineering education settings.

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